

A method to obtain the solution of the time- independent Schrödinger equation for the simple harmonic oscillator

Anirban Bose

Serampore College, Serampore, Hooghly, India.

A method has been introduced to derive the solution of the time-independent Schrödinger equation for the simple harmonic oscillator. **A trial solution has been chosen as the product of the divergent part of the approximate asymptomatic solution of the Schrödinger equation and an unknown function. By inserting this trial solution into the same equation, an equation of that unknown function is obtained. This equation has a recursive property which has been exploited to obtain the solutions of the equation. It is all about reconstruction of the equation with different solutions of that unknown function by repetitive differentiation and that ultimately leads to the wave functions of the Schrödinger equation for harmonic oscillator.**

I. INTRODUCTION

The quantum harmonic oscillator plays an important role in physics, since many potentials can be approximated as harmonic potentials near equilibrium [1]. Hence, finding the wave functions and the corresponding energies of a quantum harmonic oscillator by solving the Schrödinger equation is an indispensable part of any standard quantum textbook [1–5]. There are two different techniques, as discussed in the literature, to solve the same equation. The first is the method of power series expansion [1–5]. We guess a trial solution, part of which is a power series, and then insert it back into the Schrödinger equation. We obtain the final solution by truncating the series to a finite number of terms consistent with the energy values. The second is the ladder operator technique [1], where the Hamiltonian is expressed as the combination of these ladder operators. **There is another method [6] found in the literature where matrix algebra is used, and by embedding a (truncated) harmonic oscillator potential in an infinite square well, one can obtain extremely accurate solutions.**

In this article, we discuss another method of obtaining the wave functions and energy eigenvalues of the harmonic oscillator problem, which is different from these three methods.

Usually, in textbooks, while solving the Schrödinger equation by power series expansion, the approximate asymptotic solution of the same equation is obtained. There are two parts to the approximate asymptotic solution, one is divergent and the other is convergent. After that, a trial solution is proposed as a product of the convergent part and another unknown function, and by inserting it back to the Schrödinger equation, the unknown function is determined. In this process, one has to make sure that the unknown function does not diverge faster than the way the exponential factor converges at large distances; otherwise, their product, which is the actual solution, is divergent at large distances and is not a physically normalizable solution.

The question that may come to the curious minds of the undergraduate students is: can we explore the other way by writing the trial solution of the Schrödinger equation as a product of the divergent asymptotic part of the approximate asymptotic solution and some other function? Is it only the divergent part that decides that this trial solution will not lead to the desired solutions? What is the role of the other function in the trial solution? Is the power series expansion technique applicable in this case, too? These are important questions and, in order to get the answers, we have found another technique in which a particular recursive property of a new equation

is exploited to solve the Schrödinger equation for the harmonic potential. This new equation is obtained by inserting the trial solution into the Schrödinger equation.

II. DERIVATION OF THE SOLUTIONS OF THE HARMONIC OSCILLATOR FROM THE TIME-INDEPENDENT SCHRÖDINGER EQUATION

The time-independent Schrödinger equation is given by [7]

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{1}{2} m \omega^2 x^2 \phi = E \phi \quad (1)$$

E and $\frac{1}{2} m \omega^2 x^2$ are the total energy and the potential energy of the oscillator, respectively. We can define $\epsilon = \frac{2E}{\hbar \omega}$ and $u = \frac{x}{\alpha}$, where $\alpha = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{m \omega}}$. This makes eq.(1) dimensionless.

$$\frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial u^2} = (u^2 - \epsilon) \phi \quad (2)$$

For large u , the asymptomatic solution is

$$\phi(u) = A e^{u^2/2} + B e^{-u^2/2}, \quad (2a)$$

where A and B are constants. The first term is divergent, and the second term is convergent in the asymptomatic limit. In the power series expansion technique, the asymptomatic nature of the convergent exponential term is exploited, and the trial solution is written as $e^{-u^2/2} r(u)$. $r(u)$ is the unknown function expressed in the form of an infinite power series, and the actual structure of the power series is determined by inserting the trial solution in the Schrödinger equation. However, convergence of the asymptomatic solution ($e^{-u^2/2}$) does not ensure convergence of the actual solution ($e^{-u^2/2} r(u)$). In order to achieve the convergence of the actual solution, we have to truncate the infinite series up to a finite number of terms, and the conditions of truncation give rise to the energy eigenvalues.

Similarly, we will see that although $e^{u^2/2}$ is the divergent asymptotic solution of the harmonic oscillator problem, that does not mean that a trial solution of the actual equation, which has the form $e^{u^2/2} s(u)$, is automatically divergent. The role of $s(u)$ is of the utmost importance. If it falls faster than the increase of $e^{u^2/2}$ at large distances, then $e^{u^2/2} s(u)$ is convergent and normalizable, as observed in this method, and may be a valid acceptable solution.

So, let us try

$$\phi(u) = s(u) e^{\frac{u^2}{2}} \quad (3)$$

as the trial solution of eq.(2), and inserting it into the same equation we get

$$\frac{\partial^2 s}{\partial u^2} + 2u \frac{\partial s}{\partial u} + (\epsilon + 1)s = 0 \quad (4)$$

Let us find the ground state from Eq.(4). However, before proceeding, we must be aware of the following restrictions on $s(u)$ and ϵ as described below.

1. $s(u)$ must fall faster than the increase in the divergent exponential factor so that, according to the boundary condition, $\phi(u)$ approaches zero as u reaches infinity. This is a must for the solution to be normalizable.

2. $s(u)$ must have no nodes, so that $\phi(u)$ has no nodes. This is also a must, according to the node theorem [8–10], to be the ground state. The reason is that the higher the number of nodes means a quicker space variation of the wave function, leading to higher energy states.

3. ϵ must be positive since for a harmonic oscillator it cannot take negative values.

We already know that the approximate normalizable asymptotic wave function of the harmonic oscillator is $e^{-u^2/2}$. Since in this method the wave function is chosen as $(e^{u^2/2}s(u))$, the approximate asymptotic solution of $s(u)$ is e^{-u^2} . Interestingly, this e^{-u^2} satisfies the first two conditions mentioned above. So, can it be the ground state, too? So, to be the ground state, it must satisfy Eq.(4), and the third condition. Inserting $s = e^{-u^2}$ into Eq.(4), we find that if ϵ is 1, e^{-u^2} is the solution of Eq.(4). So, the third condition is also satisfied. Therefore, if ϵ is 1, e^{-u^2} satisfies Eq.(4) and all the three conditions mentioned above.

Under these conditions, the wave function $(e^{u^2/2}s(u))$ of the actual Schrödinger equation is normalizable and has no nodes. In addition, according to the node theorem and the orthogonality property of the solutions of the Schrödinger equation, it must be the ground state.

Let us assume that we do not know the exact ground state of the harmonic oscillator. However, that must be orthogonal to the solution derived above, since these two are the solutions of the Schrödinger equation for the same harmonic potential. According to the node theorem, for the harmonic oscillator, the ground state of the Schrödinger equation must have no nodes. However, the solution obtained by this method also has no nodes. Hence, they cannot be orthogonal because the integrand in the expression of the orthogonality relation has the same sign everywhere. Hence, only one possibility remains, that is, the solution obtained from Eq.(4) is the same as

the ground-state solution of the harmonic oscillator.

We may argue more intuitively. We have noticed that the asymptotic solution $e^{-u^2/2}$ of the Schrödinger equation is also one of the exact solutions of the Schrödinger equation. Is there any other state whose energy is less than that of $e^{-u^2/2}$? Suppose $e^{-u^2/2}$ is not the ground state: then the ground state must have energy less than the energy of the state $e^{-u^2/2}$. Now, we consider the regime where the factor $(E-V(u))$ is positive. If $\phi(u)$ is positive, then according to the Schrödinger equation the second derivative of $\phi(u)$ becomes negative and $\phi(u)$ will tend to the u-axis [11]. Similarly, if $\phi(u)$ is negative, then the second derivative of $\phi(u)$ becomes positive and once again $\phi(u)$ will tend to the u-axis. So, positive $(E-V(u))$ gives rise to the oscillatory behavior of the wave function. The higher the value of $(E-V(u))$, the faster the wave function crosses the u-axis. It is clear that $e^{-u^2/2}$ does not cross the u-axis and does not have nodes. Since the factor $(E-V(u))$ of the ground state is less than that of $e^{-u^2/2}$, the ground state will also not be able to cross the u-axis. Consequently, the number of nodes in that ground state cannot exceed the same of $e^{-u^2/2}$, and, according to the argument given in the previous paragraph, it cannot be orthogonal to $e^{-u^2/2}$. This is a contradiction. So, no such ground state can exist and $e^{-u^2/2}$ is the actual ground state.

Differentiating both sides of Eq.(4) with respect to u, we obtain the following equation.

$$\frac{\partial^3 s}{\partial u^3} + 2u \frac{\partial^2 s}{\partial u^2} + (\epsilon_0 + 3) \frac{\partial s}{\partial u} = 0 \quad (5)$$

From this equation, we may conclude that

$$\frac{\partial s}{\partial u}$$

is another solution of eq.(4) where ϵ is replaced by $\epsilon_0 + 2$.

Therefore,

$$\phi_1 = e^{\frac{u^2}{2}} \frac{\partial s}{\partial u} \quad (6)$$

is another solution of the time-independent Schrödinger equation with energy $\epsilon_0 + 2$.

Differentiating both sides of Eq.(4) n times with respect to u, we find the following.

$$\phi_n = e^{\frac{u^2}{2}} \frac{\partial^n s}{\partial u^n} \quad (7)$$

is another solution of the Schrödinger equation with energy $\epsilon_0 + 2n$. Therefore, this method gives rise to all the wave functions with their corresponding energy eigenvalues. **The normalized wave functions are**

$$\phi_n = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2^n \pi^{\frac{1}{2}} n!}} e^{-\frac{u^2}{2}} \frac{\partial^n s}{\partial u^n}. \quad (7a)$$

These wave functions are exactly the same as the wave functions of the bound states obtained by the power series expansion technique and the ladder operator method. This technique, as it appears, lies somewhere between the power series method and the ladder operator technique. Basically, in this process, the Schrödinger equation for a particular energy level is constructed from the same equation for the previous energy level.

If we apply the power series expansion technique in Eq.(4), we can see that, as energy values can not be negative for a simple harmonic oscillator, the series cannot be truncated. Therefore, we cannot find the restrictions on ϵ to take some specific values. But that was not the case while working with the usual power series expansion technique found in textbooks. In that case, the allowed values of ϵ are found in the condition of truncation of the infinite power series. However, that does not mean that we can not obtain physically acceptable normalizable solutions and the corresponding energies from Eq.(4), and we get them in a different way.

In this method, we are not really solving a differential equation directly, so we need no power series expansion. At first, we are guessing the ground state solution consistent with the underlying physics of the problem and then inserting that directly in the equation to check if it satisfies the same equation. After that, all the other normalizable solutions automatically come out with corresponding discrete energies from the differential equations, which are obtained by differentiating Eq.(4). For example, we get Eq.(5) by differentiating Eq.(4). Are they the same? No, they do not look the same. Now comes the trick. If we identify $\frac{\partial s}{\partial u}$ as s and $(\epsilon_0 + 2)$ as ϵ in Eq.(5), then Eq.(4) and Eq.(5) are exactly same and we may identify $\frac{\partial s}{\partial u}$ as another solution of Eq.(4) with eigen energy $(\epsilon_0 + 2)$. So it is really a matter of identification of the terms of the reconstructed differential equation (Eq.(5)) with the terms of the mother equation (Eq.(4)). We can generate infinite number of such differential equations by repetitively differentiating Eq.(4) and identify all the allowed eigen energies ($\epsilon_n = \epsilon_0 + 2n$, n is positive integers) with corresponding eigen functions

$(\frac{\partial^n s}{\partial u^n})$ by the same method of identification as we have done for Eq.(5). Therefore, the allowed energy values are automatically restricted.

III. DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

We begin the process with the time-independent Schrödinger equation. We make a suitable transformation so that the equation takes a particular form which has the following advantage over the original Schrödinger equation. We differentiate the new equation. We get another differential equation. However, the first equation and the one obtained by differentiating it are structurally the same, but they have different solutions with different energy values. That means we are basically solving the same equation for different energy values. This can be verified from Eq.(4) and Eq.(5). Eq.(5) is obtained by differentiating Eq.(4). If we write $s_1 = \frac{\partial s}{\partial u}$, Eq.(5) appears as

$$\frac{\partial^2 s_1}{\partial u^2} + 2u \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial u} + (\epsilon_0 + 2 + 1)s_1 = 0 \quad (8)$$

Thus, eq.(4) and eq.(8) both have the same structure but have different solutions s and $s_1 = \frac{\partial s}{\partial u}$ with corresponding energy values ϵ_0 and $\epsilon_0 + 2$ respectively.

It is interesting to see what would happen if we had started with the following trial solution.

$$\phi(u) = r(u)e^{-\frac{u^2}{2}} \quad (9)$$

Inserting the above into the time -independent Schrödinger equation, we obtain the following.

$$\frac{\partial^2 r}{\partial u^2} - 2u \frac{\partial r}{\partial u} + (\epsilon - 1)r = 0 \quad (10)$$

But, if we differentiate and write $r_1 = \frac{\partial r}{\partial u}$, we get the following equation.

$$\frac{\partial^2 r_1}{\partial u^2} - 2u \frac{\partial r_1}{\partial u} + (\epsilon - 2 - 1)r_1 = 0 \quad (11)$$

Thus, Eq.(10) and Eq.(11) both have the same structure but have different solutions r and $r_1 = \frac{\partial r}{\partial u}$ with corresponding energy values ϵ_0 and $\epsilon_0 - 2$ respectively. Therefore, by choosing the trial solution ($e^{-u^2/2}r(u)$) with the convergent exponential factor, we get Eq.(10). If we differentiate it, we get the equation of the next lower energy state as opposed to Eq.(4), which, upon differentiation, gives the equation of the next higher energy state. Therefore, Eq.(4) and Eq.(10) complement each other.

Let us guess the solution of Eq.(10). The most trivial choice is $r = 1$, and that will lead $\epsilon = 1$ to satisfy Eq.(10) and the wave function ($e^{-u^2/2}r(u)$) $\phi(u) = e^{-u^2/2}$. If we take another derivative of the equation, all terms separately become zero, since the new solution, which is the derivative of $\frac{\partial r}{\partial u}$ is zero for $r = 1$. So, no further state exists with energy less than $\epsilon = 1$. Therefore, the combination $r = 1$ and $\epsilon = 1$ is in fact the combination of the ground state, leading to the ground state wave function $\phi(u) = e^{-u^2/2}$.

$r = e^{u^2}$ is another solution of eq.(10), when $\epsilon = -1$. But that makes the final solution ($e^{\frac{-u^2}{2}}r$) of the Schrödinger equation diverge at large distances. **It indicates that the probability of finding the particle increases as we increase u , which would make the wave function unphysical and cannot be normalized.**

In this article, we understand that one can write the solution of a differential equation in various combinations of products to identify that particular combination, which will ease the process of obtaining the final solution. In the process of expansion of the power series, the combination of the product is $\phi(u) = s(u)\exp(-u^2/2)$, where the asymptotic nature of the exponential is exploited to find the solutions. In contrast, in this process, we have chosen the trial solution to be the product of such a pair of terms ($\phi(u) = \exp(u^2/2)s(u)$), so that after its substitution in the Schrödinger equation, we can exploit a particular recursive property of the transformed equation. However, in both cases, the convergence of the actual solution must be ensured, consistent with the boundary condition that the wave function must vanish at infinity.

In reality, the divergent exponential factor ($e^{(u^2/2)}$) in this method is not the issue; what matters is the convergence of the actual solution ($\phi(u) = e^{(u^2/2)}s(u)$). In this article, we have chosen a trial solution that is written as the product of an exponential and another term (s). This exponential certainly diverges at large distances, but that does not necessarily mean that the trial solution diverges at large distances, since there is another part (s) in the product which should play a crucial role in determining the nature of the actual solution. For example, for the ground state, we find that $s(u)$ is e^{-u^2} , which does not diverge at large distances, and the actual solution ($e^{u^2/2}s$) is $e^{-u^2/2}$, which is also convergent and normalizable. Moreover, choosing the divergent exponential factor ($e^{(u^2/2)}$) has an advantage. Because if the equation has to have a meaningful bound state solution, the other part ($s(u)$) of the product is compelled to converge faster than the diverging exponential factor diverges at large distances,

so that their product, which is the bound state solution, must converge at large distances.

The structure of this derivation has similarities to the usual ladder operator method. However, ladder operators are linear combinations of the momentum operator and the position operator. On the other hand, in this method, we have worked with a derivative which may be identified as the momentum operator and not as the usual ladder operators. The additional transformation that does not appear in the ladder operator method makes the difference. It leads to a differential equation whose recursive property has been exploited in this method.

There is another reason to choose the particular form of the trial solution.

If we take the derivative of Eq.(10), we get Eq.(11) in which the energy decreases by 2; otherwise, it is structurally the same as Eq.(10) with a new energy eigenfunction.

This characteristic may motivate us to find an equation that does the opposite, that is, if we differentiate it, an equation is obtained in which the energy increases, but the structure, if the derivative is identified as the new wave function, remains intact. It can be done if we can flip all the negative signs of Eq.(10), and the simplest way to achieve it is simply to change the sign of the exponential factor of the product of the trial solution and write it in $e^{u^2/2}s(u)$ form to obtain the equation we desire.

If one wants to represent the problem in the language of operator and commutation relation, one just needs to replace the derivatives by the appropriate powers of the operator D and find the following equation.

$$\hat{D}^2 s + 2\hat{u}\hat{D}s + (\epsilon + 1)s = 0 \quad (12)$$

where $\hat{D} = \frac{\partial}{\partial u}$ and the commutator relation $[\hat{D}, \hat{u}] = 1$. Since a derivative can do the job in such a simple way, we did not need to bring such technicalities at the very beginning while solving the problem.

In the end, it is basically a reconstruction of the same equation with different energy values and that is achieved by taking derivatives repetitively on Eq.(4). Therefore, the takeaway from this article is that instead of solving the Schrödinger equation directly as is done in case of method of power series expansion, if one is able to reconstruct the Schrodinger equation for any particular potential but of different energy values by some operation, he eventually determines all the eigen functions and corresponding eigen energies. The operation as observed is just a simple derivative in the case of harmonic potentials, and it is interesting to explore any other such operation for

other potentials.

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